

**ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN MASTERING HAND COMING
METHODS EFFICIENT APPLY WAYS**

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Abstract: In the article exactly English language fast and easy and efficient wants to learn has been students for language 12 learning skills given being _ student this of skills used without the language easy learn takes _

Key words : Reading skills , method, essay, Pronunciation ,Podcast,Online Voice Recorder .

Whole in the world english language the most developed language being is coming Har one student language in learning known of the methods uses _ Language of learning one how much methods there is being to 12 of them stopping we want to pass .

English language right learning 12 skills on

Abroad education get at will has been young people by the most a lot to be studied The language is , of course , English is a language He is to you Like Oxford , Harvard famous science of the gallows the door opens . Well , English language learning where level easy ? This the language how by doing faster and more efficient learning can _ Of this for the following skills on your work it is necessary

Reading

Reading skills development , grammar and language construction understanding , words in mind save , their expression and pronunciation learning important to importance have _ This is a skill take over for the following of methods your use can _

1) English book , magazine , newspaper read it

Foreign language of learning gold the rule is a lot is reading . Do not forget : this to the skill have without being standing , oral and written in tests enough level to success reach you ca n't As long as the language learning in the matter of strictly in mind you are from the internet yourself interested in the subject any book , magazine , newspaper find , regular read on.

2) Hand your phone and your computer language to English transfer

Your phone , your computer program to English change , perform your action known one word with tie up and this each day perform word your wealth increases . The same at the time social networks change the language too new knowledge in your studies help gives _

3) From mobile applications use it

Mobile equipment and applications English language learning at will those who are for infinite it is possible . Technique development lightning at speed guide going one at the time this possible use completely your at your disposal . From reading or from work home return if you are on the phone loaded one how much free of charge applications using word memorize reading and understanding your skills increases .

English to write appropriation the most difficult of qualifications is one Usually foreign _ higher study to their countries document wants to submit has been from applicants essay ,

motivational letter to write Demand will be done . Writing during short expressions instead of binders and helper sentences application , idea extended without express get very important _

4) Write a blog

Today's daily blog writing , thoughts , interests , something topic on the surface comments notice wide spread _ yourself for English open a blog . At first your suffering natural , but in your memory to " wake up " the words this method very big help gives _

5) New the words in consideration hold on

It's up to you quite a lot familiar method . new the words written paper fragments often your eye falling to the ground stick it and them each day read on. Of this the result while one how many in the day yourself you will see !

6) In the forums in debates participation eat

Descriptive art , music , theater , literature such as art types , as well as politics , technology , fashion world , cooking such as to topics your interest if so , then forums exactly you for . Interests to you near has been people with this topics about thought to exchange , to argue new words and expressions to your application impulse gives _

Listening skill by developing to go important to nature have _ Especially abroad _ education get at will has been young people went in countries difficulties , classes , seminars or in debates active participation for this skill development it is necessary

7) English song listen

Foreign language wants to develop from the first recommendations to those who have one learning in their languages a lot song is to hear . This is both words and theirs pronunciation in your study , as well as your ear stranger to words in adaptation misses _ The song listen you are his kind of easy to be understood , song of the text how much part on paper put down pay attention to what you get do it.

8) English TV channels watch do it

America and On English TV channels to the air transmitted serials , shows , news , movies to see the most useful of methods is one Initial stage subtitle with watch and then _ without writing without to understand trying see _

9) In competitions attend

Various to the nation belongs to candidates participant symposium and in competitions participation reach , experience increase _ Your pronunciation clean up to go attention look _

10) Podcast listen

Podcasts certain one in the subject vocal or pictorial are materials . Internet podcasts ease with growing up main tool _ Loved in your topics broadcasts listening little by little this about your skills increases , to you motivation gives _

" I understand , but speak " I can't take it . " words to our ears is played . Abroad the work giver organizations are also TOYeFL or IYeLTS such as from tests received to your certificates not speech _ skills where level to your possession attention looks _ So this is it important _

11) Yourself talk and write

Communication to do skills development for the most efficient of methods one last times famous has been online and free of charge sound to write are programs . Your speech writing take it , mother language English has been to your friend your listening , your mistakes if so , from them help you ask can _

12) English speaking friends increase

Communication do it get your skills development for english speaking friends increase _ on the Internet many sites cultures with dating , foreign language study of the world different from countries friend gain for intended are platforms . Also like Telegram, WhatsApp , Skype applications using your comrades with live conversation to build you have a chance .

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